

Experimental backward integration for state-dependent differential Riccati equation (SDDRE): A case study on flapping-wing flying robot

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ABSTRACT

Backward integration (BI) is a classical approach for solving optimal control arising from linear quadratic regulator (LQR) design in differential form. It proposes a two-round solution, the first one starting from a final boundary condition to the initial one to generate the optimal gain, and the next one, solving the control system in a forward loop. Implementation of the BI on the nonlinear optimal control, the state-dependent differential Riccati equation (SDDRE), is a challenge since in the backward loop, the state information is missing and is not straightforward like the LQR. Hence, a control for backward motion is required to regulate the system from the terminal to the initial desired states. While there have been some valuable works on the theoretical implementation of the BI in simulations for the SDDRE, this approach has not been reported in experiments for the best knowledge of the authors. Here in this work, the SDDRE is solved using the BI and two backward and forward solution steps, and it is experimentally applied for a flapping-wing flying robot (FWFR). The execution of the control system is done onboard using Raspberry Pi 4B as the processor which has limited computational capacity. The trajectory tracking of a line in a closed limited space is proposed for the FWFR flight. The objective is to position the robot bird at the corner of the rectangular limited space with minimum error in translation. The results have been presented for 21 flights to show the repeatability and presented the best-case minimum error of 10 (cm) at the end of the trajectory, in the YZ-plane. Considering approximately 12 (m) flight path, the error is found less than 1 percent of the travel distance. The results were compared with forward integration to confirm the correctness of the computation. The experimental flight dataset, MATLAB simulation codes, and experimental Python codes are available as supplementary material for this work in the online version of the paper.

1. Introduction

Offering the best (optimal) trade-off between the performance and energy in control systems is one of the prime motivations behind using optimal control policies. This benefit usually comes with the cost of solving complex equations in different branches of optimal control. Linear quadratic regulator (LQR) is one of the nearly all popular techniques in the control engineering community (Byrski et al., 2024; Dai & Sznaier, 2023; Lu et al., 2023), available in two versions of algebraic and differential Riccati equations. Algebraic Riccati equation presents infinite-horizon control and differential Riccati equation (DRE) with a final boundary condition results in finite-horizon control (Anderson & Moore, 2007; Kirk, 1998). A classical method to solve the DRE is backward integration (BI) which is a two-round solution (Choi et al., 2023). The first backward round starts from the final boundary condition to the initial one to record the optimal gain, the positive definite answer

to the DRE. The recorded optimal gain can then be used in the forward solution to regulate the system from the initial condition toward the desired states. The application of the BI on the LQR is possible since the system matrices, $\{\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}\}$, along with the weighting matrices $\{\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{R}\}$ are all linear and do not depend on state information, where they represent a linear system, $\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}(t)$, with a corresponding cost function $J = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{\infty} \{\mathbf{u}^T(t)\mathbf{R}\mathbf{u}(t) + \mathbf{x}^T(t)\mathbf{Q}\mathbf{x}(t)\} dt$, in which $\mathbf{x}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $\mathbf{u}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^m$ are state and input vectors, respectively. This point will become a challenge for the nonlinear optimal control where state information exists in system matrices $\{\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t)), \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}(t))\}$.

The implementation of optimality conditions on the Hamilton–Jacobi–Bellman (HJB) equation provides optimal nonlinear control laws, which can be solved through various methods including successive Galerkin approximation (Almubarak et al., 2021; Wang & Li, 2020), state-dependent Riccati equation (SDRE) approach (Mlayeh

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Table 1
Nomenclature.

$\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t))$	SDC matrix	$r(t)$	Angular velocity around z-axis
$\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}(t))$	SDC matrix, coeff. of inputs	$\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{x}(t))$	Weighting matrix of inputs
$\mathbf{C}(\xi_2(t), \xi_2(t))$	Coriolis and centrifugal matrix	t	Time
$e_i(t)$	Error variable	t_f	Final time
$\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}(t))$	System vector	$\mathbf{T}(\xi_2(t))$	Rotation matrix
\mathbf{F}	Weighting matrix at final time	$\mathbf{u}(t)$	Input vector
$\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}(t))$	System vector, coeff. of inputs	$u_{\text{flapping}}(t)$	Input flapping
J	Cost function integral	$u_{\text{lateral}}(t)$	Input rudder
$\mathbf{J}(\xi_2(t))$	Inertia matrix FWFR	$\mathbf{u}_0(t)$	Input orientation dynamics
$\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t))$	Sub-optimal control gain	$\mathbf{x}(t)$	State vector
m	Number of inputs	$\mathbf{x}_{\text{des}}(t)$	Desired state vector
\mathbf{M}_x	Mixer matrix	$x_c(t)$	Position in x-axis
n	Number of states	$y_c(t)$	Position in y-axis
$p(t)$	Angular velocity around x-axis	$z_c(t)$	Position in z-axis
PWM ₀	Zero PWM to the motors	$\theta(t)$	Pitch angle
PWM _i	PWM to the motors	$\xi_2(t)$	Euler angles
$q(t)$	Angular velocity around y-axis	$\mathbf{v}_2(t)$	Angular velocity
$\mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x}(t))$	Weighting matrix of states	$\phi(t)$	Roll angle
$\mathbf{Q}^{1/2}(\mathbf{x}(t))$	Cholesky decomposition	$\psi(t)$	Yaw angle

& Khedher, 2024; Nekoo et al., 2024), power-series approximation (Kennedy & Tran, 2015), multivariable B-spline (Govindarajan et al., 2014), iterative algorithm (Amini et al., 2020), etc. While the stability proof of the nonlinear optimal control with respect to linear one is a challenge, the benefits of that persuade the researchers to apply it to complex systems. Some advantages can be listed as nonlinear structure, obtaining closer results to reality, robust properties, limit-cycle exhibition, bifurcation, chaos, easier tuning, etc. Here in this work, the central attention is on the SDRE control design, a popular tool for solving optimal control problems, a nonlinear solution to the HJB equation.

The SDRE was introduced by Pearson in the 60 s as an approximation suboptimal solution to optimal control (Pearson, 1962). It gained attention and theoretical development, i.e. Burghart (1969), Wernli and Cook (1975), though the exponential growth of the SDRE began in the 90 s in theory and application, specifically in aerospace (Cloutier, 1997; Cloutier & Zipfel, 1999; Stansbery & Cloutier, 2000). The SDRE mimics the LQR design in the derivation of suboptimal control by the implementation of optimality conditions on the Hamiltonian function. Similar to that, it releases two basic versions of algebraic SDRE and the state-dependent differential Riccati equation (SDDRE) controller (Cimen, 2012). The differential version is accompanied by a final boundary condition and presents a finite-horizon suboptimal structure (Nekoo, 2019). Some solutions to the algebraic SDRE can be named as an exact solution (Banks et al., 2007) which is ideal for practical implementation, the Schur method (Laub, 1979), power series approximation (PSA) method (Banks et al., 2007), etc. The PSA generated an attractive offline method to skip the online solution in experimental implementations, or better to say a more “practical” approach (Do et al., 2013). The technological leap in recent years has led to the use of more numerical methods in solving the Riccati equation (Korayem & Lademakhi, 2024), and the application of the Schur method for solving SDRE at each time step of simulation. The command “care” is a function to compute the gain of the SDRE numerically in MATLAB software and is also available in Python with the control-PyPI library.

The SDDRE was popular in robotic manipulator control (Korayem & Lademakhi, 2023; Nasiri et al., 2024), offering rapid convergence close to the final boundary condition; moreover, in other control systems, it was widely used. Lin et al. employed the differential Riccati controller for maneuvering-target interception (Lin et al., 2023). Reducing the computational burden of the SDDRE was the objective of the research. The SDDRE is not in nature a robust controller though it can handle external force in the control structure; an example was shown for an underwater manipulator mounted on an autonomous vehicle (Kabanov et al., 2022). Controlling a drone with an application of payload transportation (Guerrero-Sánchez et al., 2021), wheeled mobile robot (Makarov, 2021), and spacecraft attitude control (Khamis

& Zydek, 2020), were also reported in the literature, confirming the effectiveness and application of the SDDRE in control systems.

The final boundary of the SDDRE offers interesting finite-time characteristics to manipulate the final time, in a good sense, to make the system faster in control response. By increasing the weighting matrix of states at the terminal time, the gain becomes bigger and increases the control inputs to act faster (Lin et al., 2023). The common solution methods for the SDDRE are backward integration (Korayem & Nekoo, 2015b), the Lyapunov-based method (LBM) (Heydari & Balakrishnan, 2015), and the state-transition matrix (STM) method (Jung et al., 2013; Korayem & Nekoo, 2014). The LBM and STM presented a one-round forward solution to the SDDRE and were used more in the literature than the BI due to its challenging two-round solution. Despite the one or two rounds of solutions, there is a technical issue with the BI for the SDDRE, the existence of states in the system $\{\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t)), \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}(t))\}$ and weighting matrices $\{\mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x}(t)), \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{x}(t))\}$.

To integrate from the terminal boundary condition to the initial one, if state information is needed, the trajectory of the system in backward motion will become important. Optimal control policy intends to present suboptimal gain for the trajectory of the system from initial to desired states. If the backward motion generates the gain for another trajectory rather than the intended one for forward motion, then the optimality is lost! So, for the regulation (point-to-point) control, the SDRE was used to control the system in the backward motion (Korayem & Nekoo, 2015a). This deviation from optimality is reduced for trajectory tracking cases since the forward and backward motions match. All the mentioned concerns avoided the experimental implementation of this solution method for nonlinear systems. In this current work, the two-round BI is utilized to find the answer to the state-dependent differential Riccati equation with experimental tests. The theory and simulation of the SDDRE and the BI were already presented in the literature, and this current work focuses on the experimental implementation of that and addressing the challenge of access to state information in the backward integration stage.

The SDRE has been widely applied to various fields of control engineering such as aerospace, robotics, unmanned aerial vehicles, hydraulics systems, satellite control, drug administration, etc. One of the recent controlled case studies of the method scored remarkable results in aerial robotics. Flapping-wing flying robots (FWFRs) show challenging behavior in the dynamics and control of the flights due to the excessive disturbance of the flapping action by the wings. The primary implemented control methods for the FWFR are listed as proportional-integral-derivative (PID) (Wenfu et al., 2022; Zhong et al., 2023), adaptive control (Maldonado et al., 2020; Mousavi & Pourtakdoust, 2023), LQR (Abbasi et al., 2022), etc. The SDRE has also been applied to the FWFR in point-to-point control in a confined space, and indoor experimentation (Nekoo & Ollero, 2023a). The solution to the Riccati

equation was done online at each time step using Python and the “care” command from the control library. This solution generated the gain for the algebraic SDRE, infinite horizon case.

Motivation. Why the BI method is particularly apt for the FWFR control and how it effectively tackles the intricacies inherent in nonlinear control, especially concerning the challenge of state information scarcity in the backward recursion process — an aspect that warrants further elaboration within this work! The FWFR either lands on a specific area or perches on a branch (Zufferey et al., 2022). Both landing and perching cases should be precise, specifically at the end of the trajectory. The SDDRE is a differential equation that penalizes the final boundary condition. This can be interpreted as more precision at the final time which is the end of the trajectory or perching point. By increasing the final penalty of the SDDRE weighting matrix adequately, future applications might be achieved with more reliability. The other reason for the selection of the BI (with an unpleasant two-round solution) is to address the challenge of state information in the backward loop. An ideal method for solving the SDDRE would be a one-round forward solution method; however, backward integration as a classical method in optimal control has been an interesting topic for this research to be addressed experimentally.

Contributions:

- C1. Experimental implementation of backward integration to solve state-dependent differential Riccati equation.
- C2. Finite-time SDDRE flight control on flapping-wing flying robot in limited indoor space. The previous SDRE implementation was done in infinite-horizon suboptimal control (Nekoo & Ollero, 2023a), which motivated this work to change the control from algebraic to differential form.
- C3. Line trajectory tracking in indoor closed space via a large-scale 1.6 (m) wingspan FWFR, motivated from Nekoo and Ollero (2023a), which only considered point-to-point control.

Notation. The transpose operation of a matrix or a vector is denoted by $(\cdot)^T$, n -dimensional Euclidean space is shown by \mathbb{R}^n , $\mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ shows an $n \times m$ real matrix, $\mathbf{0}_{n \times n}$ and $\mathbf{I}_{n \times n}$ denote zero and identity matrices of size $n \times n$, respectively, $\text{int}(\cdot)$ is an integer-valued function, and $\text{diag}(\cdot)$ denotes a matrix with diagonal components. The rest of the parameters are defined in the nomenclature, Table 1.

Context. Section 2 states the SDDRE control structure and governing equations. The conditions and details of the backward integration solution method are expressed in Section 3. Simulation analysis is expressed in Section 4. The experimental platform and the flight data are presented in Sections 5 and 6, respectively. Concluding remarks and a summary of the work are mentioned in Section 7.

2. Optimal control structure: SDDRE

The system is defined as a nonlinear, time-invariant, and affine-in-control equation:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}(t)) + \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t)), \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t)) : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ and $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}(t)) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ are piecewise continuous vector-valued smooth functions, that satisfy the local Lipschitz condition. The state vector is indicated by $\mathbf{x}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and the input vector by $\mathbf{u}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^m$ in which m is the number of inputs and n the number of states. System (1) is reshaped to the state-dependent coefficient (SDC) parameterization (Çimen, 2008):

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{u}(t), \quad (2)$$

where:

$$\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}(t)) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}, \quad \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t)) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}.$$

Assumption 1. The SDC pair of $\{\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t)), \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}(t))\}$ in (2), represents a completely controllable parameterization of the nonlinear system (1) for all $\mathbf{x}(t)$ in $t \in [0, t_f]$ in which t_f is the final time (Nekoo, 2019).

Fig. 1. The block diagram of backward integration using LQR.

The nonlinear optimal control policy (cost function) is addressed through the integral:

$$J(\cdot) = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{t_f} [\mathbf{x}^T(t) \mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{u}^T(t) \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{u}(t)] dt + \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{x}^T(t_f) \mathbf{F} \mathbf{x}(t_f), \quad (3)$$

where weighting matrices $\mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x}(t)) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ and $\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{x}(t)) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$ penalize the states and inputs in $t \in [0, t_f]$, and $\mathbf{F} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ penalizes the states at the final time. $\mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x}(t))$ and \mathbf{F} are symmetric positive semi-definite matrices and $\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{x}(t))$ is symmetric positive definite.

Assumption 2. The SDC pair of $\{\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t)), \mathbf{Q}^{1/2}(\mathbf{x}(t))\}$ in (2)–(3), represents a completely observable parameterization of the nonlinear system (1) for all $\mathbf{x}(t)$ in $t \in [0, t_f]$ in which $\mathbf{Q}^{1/2}(\mathbf{x}(t))$ is Cholesky decomposition of $\mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x}(t))$ (Nekoo, 2019).

The SDDRE control law is:

$$\mathbf{u}(t) = -\mathbf{R}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{B}^T(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{x}(t), \quad (4)$$

in which the nonlinear suboptimal gain of the controller is $\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t)) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, positive-definite symmetric answer to the SDDRE (Cimen, 2012):

$$-\dot{\mathbf{K}}(\mathbf{x}(t)) = \mathbf{A}^T(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t)) + \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t)) + \mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x}(t)) - \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{R}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{B}^T(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t)), \quad (5)$$

with terminal boundary condition $\mathbf{K}(t_f) = \mathbf{F}$.

The stability of the SDDRE controller is addressed by the second Lyapunov method. The Lyapunov candidate is selected as:

$$V(\mathbf{x}(t)) = \mathbf{x}^T(t) \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{x}(t),$$

where $V(\mathbf{x}(t)) = 0$ if and only if $\mathbf{x}(t) = 0$, $V(\mathbf{x}(t)) > 0$ if and only if $\mathbf{x}(t) \neq 0$ since $\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t)) > 0$, and finally, $\dot{V}(\mathbf{x}(t)) < 0$ must hold for $\mathbf{x}(t) \neq 0$. The derivative of the Lyapunov candidate results in (Nekoo, 2019):

$$\dot{V}(\mathbf{x}(t)) = -\mathbf{x}^T(t) \{ \mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x}(t)) + \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{R}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{B}^T(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \} \mathbf{x}(t),$$

which proves the stability considering that $\mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x}(t))$ and $\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{x}(t))$ are positive. The controllability and observability conditions must be satisfied to find $\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t))$ and guarantee the stability using the Lyapunov approach.

3. Backward integration solution

The BI is a classical approach to finding an answer to the differential Riccati equation. It is easy to implement that on linear systems since the matrices are independent of state information. The flow of the solution for linear optimal control is presented in Fig. 1.

The inputs to the first round of solution are linear (constant) system and weighting matrices to the DRE. The solution generates a time-varying optimal gain $\mathbf{K}(t)$. The gain is substituted in the forward closed loop using the LQR control law, applied to the linear system. This procedure will become different for nonlinear systems due to the existence of state information in the system matrices. For the regulation case, the trajectory of the backward and forward motion might not match

and it is required that a controller regulates the system from terminal point to zero state condition (Korayem & Nekoo, 2015a). The trajectory tracking case, zero error in backward integration is ideal, therefore, the desired trajectory can be fed to the system to update $\{B(x(t)), A(x(t))\}$ and weighting matrices $\{Q(x(t)), R(x(t))\}$ by substituting $x(t) \rightarrow x_{des}(t)$ in which “des” denotes “desired”. The process of the BI solution to nonlinear systems is shown in Fig. 2. Contrary to the linear one, the matrices must be updated by states at each time step of backward integration to generate suboptimal gain $K(x(t))$. In the forward closed loop, there is no need to solve the Riccati like conventional SDRE and the gain directly is used in the controller. The matrices $B(x(t)), R(x(t))$ are only needed to be updated for the control law (4). The governing SDDRE Eq. (5) is only solved in the backward control loop.

There are other solution methods for SDDRE including the Lyapunov-based method and the STM approach, both offering single-forward solutions. Both LBM and STM are limited to solving only standard Riccati Eq. (5). The first advantage of the BI is that it is not limited to the shape of the equation, and it can be used to solve the modified or complete SDDRE equation. It is known that the application of optimality conditions on the HJB results in a complete differential equation (Nekoo & Ollero, 2023a):

$$-\dot{K}(x) = A^T(x)K(x) + K(x)A(x) + Q(x) - K(x)B(x)R^{-1}(x)B^T(x)K(x) + \left(\frac{\partial A(x)}{\partial x}x\right)^T K(x) + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial Q(x)}{\partial x}x\right)^T + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial R(x)}{\partial x}R^{-1}(x)B^T(x)K(x)x\right)^T R^{-1}(x)B^T(x)K(x) + \left(\frac{\partial B(x)}{\partial x}R^{-1}(x)B^T(x)K(x)x\right)^T K(x), \quad (6)$$

which presents the complete form of the SDDRE (5). The BI can solve (6) and is independent of the shape of the equation. This flexibility in the shape of the equation helped in the incorporation of a constraint within the suboptimal control which was an example of the application of satellite regulation (Nekoo et al., 2023).

The second advantage is that it does not depend on a library to calculate the answer. The LBM needs the solution to SDRE and a state-dependent Lyapunov equation to complete the answer. This will create again the delay in practical implementations since the use of the “care” command or the Schur method becomes necessary.

4. Simulation

4.1. Regulation

Consider a nonlinear system:

$$\dot{x}(t) = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 0 & x_2(t) \end{bmatrix}}_{A(x(t))} x(t) + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}}_B u(t),$$

with weighting matrices:

$$R = 1, Q = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

and the simulation is in 10 s, the final states are to be penalized by $F = \text{diag}(2, 0)$. The initial condition is $x(0) = [0.5, 0]^T$ and the final one is chosen as $x_{des} = [-0.5, 0]^T$. The backward control loop from the final to initial states is regulated with the modified control law:

$$u(t) = -R^{-1}(x(t))B^T(x(t))K_{SDRE}(x(t))[x(t) - x(0)],$$

with final condition $x(t_f) = x_{des}$ and $K(t_f) = F$. x_{des} is the desired state vector of the control system, in the regulation case that is constant and is set at the final time, and in trajectory tracking, it can be time-varying $x_{des}(t)$. $K_{SDRE}(x(t))$ is the control gain of the backward motion that regulates the states from final to initial condition. Since the controller is not built yet, a conventional SDRE controller provides the gain for

Fig. 2. The block diagram of backward integration using SDDRE for trajectory tracking.

Fig. 3. The control gains of the SDDRE using backward integration and comparison with conventional SDRE. (a) $K_{11}(x(t))$, (b) $K_{12}(x(t))$, (c) $K_{22}(x(t))$.

the backward regulation $K_{SDRE}(x(t))$. The comparison of the gains of the SDDRE and the SDRE is shown in Fig. 3.

Since the gains are found by numerical solutions, a parametric representation of the gains is not available. The states and control laws of the SDDRE and conventional SDRE are demonstrated in Fig. 4. The components of the control gain of the SDDRE started from the final condition F and passed the transient zone close to the final time and reached the steady state solution approaching $t \rightarrow 0$. Since the final and initial conditions of the simulation were chosen symmetric, the steady state solution of the SDDRE and the SDRE matched. This symmetric motion is presented in Fig. 4(a)–(b), labeled by “backward state regulation”, plotted with red color. This indicates that in regulation control cases, the forward and backward trajectories do not match, which is a drawback. Despite this difference in trajectories, the results of the regulation control using the SDDRE outperform the SDRE. The error of the SDDRE was gained 1.064×10^{-4} and for the SDRE 0.0012. This error reduction was found despite the less cost function value: $J_{SDDRE} = 1.1431$ and $J_{SDRE} = 1.2557$. The advantage of the regulation case is the reduction of the final time to manipulate the system response, to be faster. The detailed data on the error and the cost function values are stated in Table 2. To get even better results in the comparison, the weighting matrix of states at the terminal could be increased.

4.2. Trajectory tracking

The effect of the final boundary condition on the drastic error reduction close to the terminal point was observed in the regulation case study in Section 4.1. The trajectory tracking control case presents a time-dependent path for the controller to follow and this makes the

Fig. 4. The state variables and control inputs of the simulation in the regulation case study. (a) The first state, (b) the second state, (c) the input signal.

Table 2

The error and cost function value of the SDDRE in comparison with the SDRE for different final times.

No.	t_f	Error SDDRE	Error SDRE	J_{SDDRE}	J_{SDRE}
1	10	1.0640×10^{-4}	0.0012	1.1431	1.2557
2	9	1.9558×10^{-4}	0.0017	1.0201	1.1314
3	8	0.0010	3.4345×10^{-4}	0.8931	1.0070
4	7	0.0024	0.0058	0.7566	0.8809
5	6	0.0027	0.0192	0.6072	0.7499
6	5	0.0047	0.0353	0.4514	0.6106

role of the final boundary condition vague since the performance of the tracking in the entire time history of the trajectory is important. The application of the SDDRE using BI solution for trajectory tracking case puts more effort close to final time (F) and also controls the path with corresponding Q and R . This possibility motivated this work to use finite-time SDDRE tracking to attain more precision in the position control at the end of the trajectory.

A controller was needed for the regulation of the states backward in Section 4.1; however, in trajectory tracking, one option is to use the desired states directly in the SDC matrices $\{B(x(t)), A(x(t))\}$ and weighting matrices $\{Q(x(t)), R(x(t))\}$ to update them in each time-step of the control loop. Here in this subsection, an example is reviewed using BI with the desired states in the backward loop. Consider a nonlinear system:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -0.2x_1(t) + 2 \cos(x_1(t)x_2(t)) & -x_2(t) \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}(t) + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} u(t),$$

with corresponding weighting matrices $R = 1$ and $Q = \text{diag}(1, 1)$. The desired trajectory is defined as $\mathbf{x}_{\text{des}}(t) = [\sin \omega t, \omega \cos \omega t]^T$ in which $\omega = 0.5$ defines the speed of the oscillatory trajectory. The simulation time is defined $t_f = 30$ (s) with final boundary condition $F = 10 \times Q$. The initial and final conditions of the simulation are set as $\mathbf{x}(0) = [0, 0.5]^T$ and $\mathbf{x}(t_f) = [0.6503, -0.3798]^T$, respectively. The control gains are demonstrated in Fig. 5. The state and input information are shown in Fig. 6. The error of the trajectory tracking is presented in Fig. 6-(d), showing better performance for the SDDRE. It should be highlighted that the final error of the SDDRE 0.5947 was remarkably lower than the SDRE 0.8049. The cost function values were also obtained $J_{SDDRE} = 119.5695$ and $J_{SDRE} = 125.3978$.

4.3. Analysis: Weighting matrix and disturbance

A brief analysis is performed to show the role of the weighting matrix and disturbance on the performance of the controller. The first

Fig. 5. The control gains of the SDDRE for the tracking case and comparison with the traditional SDRE. (a) $K_{11}(x(t))$, (b) $K_{12}(x(t))$, (c) $K_{22}(x(t))$.

Fig. 6. The data of the simulation in the tracking case study. (a) The first state, (b) the second state, (c) the input signal, (d) the error of the tracking.

set of simulations shows changes in the weighting matrix of states $Q = b \times I_{2 \times 2}$ in which $b = [0.1, 0.5, 1, 2, 5, 10, 50, 100]$. Different values for b increase the weighting matrix, and an increase in Q , increases the precision. The error and cost function values are reported in Table 3. So, we expect to reach better performance and that would show the effect of tuning on the results, presented in Fig. 7. The next analysis is the effect of disturbance on the performance of the SDDRE controller. The disturbed system is represented as:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{A}(x(t))\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{B}(x(t))\mathbf{u}(t) + \mathbf{d}(t),$$

where $\mathbf{d}(t) = [0, a \times \{\mathbb{H}(t - 12) - \mathbb{H}(t - 18)\}]^T$ is the disturbance vector in which $a = [0.5, 1, 2, 4, 5, 7]$ and $\mathbb{H}(t - 12)$ is a heaviside step function. The disturbance adds a change in the dynamics in the middle of the simulation. The results of the trajectory tracking are presented in Fig. 8 which shows the successful compensation after the disturbance and similar tracking error at the final time.

Fig. 7. The results of input signals (a), and errors (b), changing the weighting matrix of states.

Table 3

The cost function and error values for simulations with various weighting matrices for states.

b	0.1	0.5	1	2	5	10	50	100
$J_{\text{SDRE}} \times 10^3$	0.0964	0.1079	0.1195	0.1397	0.1920	0.2683	0.7760	1.3503
Error	1.8270	1.4963	1.2422	0.9179	0.5652	0.3964	0.1772	0.1332

5. Experimental setup: FWFR

The FWFR is a challenging prototype for control implementation. The system should be lightweight less than 1 (kg), and the current weight is 623.8 (g) without the battery. The power supply is provided by a LiPo 450 (mAh) battery, 4 cells, with 14.8 (V) and weight of 57.3 (g). This small battery supports the processor, Raspberry Pi 4 digital board, flapping wing motor, and three servomotors for the tails. The flapping is produced by a brushless direct current Hacker motor A20-26M through a set of gears with a reduction ratio of 1:42. The servomotors of the tail are SH-0255MG powered by 5 (V) signal through the LM7805 regulator. The hardware detail of the FWFR is presented in Fig. 9.

The flight zone is a limited closed space $20 \times 15 \times 7$ (m) area covered by a safety net which provides approximately 15 (m) diagonal distance. The position and orientation of the FWFR are trackable in this area by the OptiTrack system. The motion capture system has 28 cameras to cover the area and the precision is approximately less than 2 (mm) in positioning. The frequency of the data streaming is set to 120 (fps), frame per second. Passive markers are used to detect the FWFR, presented by shining balls in Fig. 9, right side.

The SDDRE is a model-based suboptimal control approach. The modeling of the flapping-wing robots is challenging due to the complexity of the computation in lift/thrust and its interference with the motion of the system. An alternative way to model this system for simulations is equivalent modeling of the wings by base-excitation, a famous method in mechanical vibrations (Nekoo & Ollero, 2023b). Wings apply periodic disturbance to the center-of-mass (CoM) of the FWFR, and as a result, a periodic oscillatory motion is observable in all flight trajectories in the Z-axis direction. This modeling presents the motion through an equivalent mass–spring–damper linked to the body of the bird. The motion of the FWFR is subjected to some assumptions such as the existence of a minimum forward velocity in flight for the

Fig. 8. The effect of disturbance on the SDDRE performance in tracking, input signals (a), and errors (b).

stability of the motion, and neglecting position control in X-axis (forward direction) (Nekoo & Ollero, 2023a). The origin of the latter is due to the underactuation of the robot; the configuration of the tail provides control in roll, pitch, and yaw coupled with height and lateral motion control. The flapping frequency also contributes to height control as an active parameter which sums up the total number of actuators to 4.

The orientation dynamics of the FWFR present a nonlinear system that is coupled to the translation dynamics. The SDC parameterization of the orientation is expressed as (Nekoo & Ollero, 2023a):

$$\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t)) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{T}(\xi_2(t)) \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & -\mathbf{T}^{-1}(\xi_2(t))\mathbf{J}^{-1}(\xi_2(t))\mathbf{C}(\xi_2(t), \dot{\xi}_2(t))\mathbf{T}(\xi_2(t)) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}(t)) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{T}^{-1}(\xi_2(t))\mathbf{J}^{-1}(\xi_2(t)) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{x}(t) = [\xi_2(t), \mathbf{v}_2(t)]^\top$ is the state vector, $\xi_2(t) = [\phi(t), \theta(t), \psi(t)]^\top$ (rad) is the Euler angles and $\mathbf{v}_2(t) = [p(t), q(t), r(t)]^\top$ (rad/s) is the angular velocity of the FWFR. The inertia matrix of the robot is denoted by $\mathbf{J}(\xi_2(t)) : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ and Coriolis and centrifugal terms are collected in the vector $[\mathbf{C}(\xi_2(t), \dot{\xi}_2(t))\dot{\xi}_2(t)] : \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$, and:

$$\mathbf{T}(\xi_2(t)) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & s_\phi t_\theta & c_\phi t_\theta \\ 0 & c_\phi & -s_\phi \\ 0 & s_\phi/c_\theta & c_\phi/c_\theta \end{bmatrix}. \quad (9)$$

These SDC matrices are used for the attitude control of the robot in the experimental implementation of backward and forward control loops. They are linked to the linear PID design on the translation control and all together, track the predefined trajectory in the flight.

The operating system of the Raspberry Pi 4 is Ubuntu 20.04 for onboard processing. The communication between the OptiTrack, and Python code is presented in Fig. 10. The position and orientation feedback is read by the ROS1 and virtual-reality peripheral network (VRPN), communicating with the main control code. Python3 is used as the main programming language. It has the main backward and forward control loops and receives the feedback data from ROS1.

The flow of the code and BI implementation is as follows. The first step is to find a proper final boundary condition \mathbf{F} for the backward loop. A scale value of the steady-state gain of the SDRE is chosen for the final boundary condition, i.e. $\mathbf{F} = a \times \mathbf{K}_{\text{SDRE}}(\mathbf{x}(t_f))$ where a is an arbitrary positive constant. This process needs a one-time answer to the algebraic Riccati equation based on the final desired states to find $\mathbf{K}_{\text{SDRE}}(\mathbf{x}(t_f))$. Since this step is outside the backward loop, the delay is not affecting the integration process. In the next step, the robot should be held on the

Fig. 9. The FWFR: (left) hardware detail and electronics, (right) robot bird.

Fig. 10. The communication details of the experimental platform.

terminal point with the desired orientation at t_f , as precise as possible. Considering that the flight path is approximately 12 to 15 (m), there is room for a little error in the placement of the robot at the final point. The backward loop starts and the robot is moved back towards the initial condition of the flight, walking through the flight zone. The speed of walking backward ≈ 10 (s) is slower than the forward flight ≈ 4 (s) and the justification of this incompatibility is needed.

There are two zones in solution, transient and steady-state response, Fig. 3, as one can see the backward motion on the gain signals starts from final time to the middle of the simulation time $10 \rightarrow 5$ (s) and stays on steady-state values till the end of the integration. So, if the computation of the optimal gain backward in time increases more than the needed flight time, it will be cut from the steady state value of the gains. In other words, the ≈ 4 last seconds of the control gain will be used in the forward flight. There is a pause after the backward integration loop to put the FWFR on the launcher in the right spot and get ready for launching the robot. Then the forward loop starts and the robot is launched using the recorded gain $\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t))$ in the BI loop. Based on the discussion and results in Section 4.2, the desired trajectory information is fed to the system and consequently, there is no need for actuation (flapping and tail motion) in the backward loop.

6. Experimental results

6.1. Flight and comparison with SDRE

The initial reference frame is placed at the center of the OptiTrack which defines the origin of the workspace. The initial condition of the flight is defined for position $\{x_c(0), y_c(0), z_c(0)\} = \{-5.34, 3.54, 1.71\}$ (m) and orientation $\{\phi(0), \theta(0), \psi(0)\} = \{0, -0.24, -0.55\}$ (rad) which is the coordinate of the end of the launcher. The initial velocity for all generalized coordinates is zero except for the forward motion $\dot{x}_c(0) = 4$ (m/s). The desired condition at the end of the flight path for the position is $\{x_c(t_f), y_c(t_f), z_c(t_f)\} = \{8, -3.5, 2.3\}$ (m) and orientation $\{\phi(t_f), \theta(t_f), \psi(t_f)\} = \{0, -0.7, -0.55\}$ (rad). The motion of the robot is almost linear in forward flight, approximately $\dot{x}_c(t) \approx 3-4$ (m/s) similar to the initial condition. Hence, the lateral linear trajectory is designed through the motion in the X -axis: $y_c(t) = x_c(t) \tan \psi(t_f)$.

The weighting matrices are chosen as:

$$\mathbf{Q} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.01 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.01 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.01 \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{R} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix},$$

and the final boundary condition as $\mathbf{F} = 2 \times \mathbf{K}_{\text{SDRE}}(\mathbf{x}(t_f))$. The inverted matrix of the mixer, which maps the torque input of the SDDRE to the pulse-width-modulation (PWM) scale for the tails, is set as:

$$\mathbf{M}_x^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 300 \\ -150 & 150 & 0 \\ -150 & -150 & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

The control law for orientation is:

$$\mathbf{u}_0(t) = -\mathbf{M}_x^{-1} \mathbf{R}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{B}^\top(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t)) [\mathbf{x}(t) - \mathbf{x}_{\text{des}}].$$

Linear PID control designs are employed for height and lateral control:

$$u_{\text{flapping}}(t) = -50e_z(t) - 4\dot{e}_z(t) - 2 \int_0^t e_z(\tau) d\tau,$$

$$u_{\text{lateral}}(t) = -50e_y(t) - \dot{e}_y(t) - 5 \int_0^t e_y(\tau) d\tau,$$

where $e_i(t) = x_i(t) - x_{\text{des},i}$ is the i th error variable. Now the controllers are arranged for the actuation of the motors as PWM signals:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \text{PWM}_{\text{flapping}} \\ \text{PWM}_{\text{rudder}} \\ \text{PWM}_{\text{elevator, right}} \\ \text{PWM}_{\text{elevator, left}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \text{int}(u_{\text{flapping}}(t)) \\ \text{int}(u_{0,1}(t) + u_{\text{lateral}}(t)) \\ \text{int}(u_{0,2}(t)) \\ \text{int}(u_{0,3}(t)) \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \text{PWM}_{\text{flapping},0} \\ \text{PWM}_{\text{rudder},0} \\ \text{PWM}_{\text{elevator, right},0} \\ \text{PWM}_{\text{elevator, left},0} \end{bmatrix},$$

in which $\text{int}(\cdot)$ is an integer function, and i.e. $\text{PWM}_{i,0}$ is zero PWM signal that puts the actuators in equilibrium points of the tails; or minimum frequency for flapping to keep steady-state flight (a constant integer).

The state information, the generalized coordinates of the FWFR, are shown in Fig. 11, moving from the initial towards the terminal condition, tracking the diagonal line. The velocity states are demonstrated in Fig. 12. The velocity of the forward flight obtained approximately 3 (m/s) in the tracking. The PWM signals of the flapping and servomotors of the tails are shown in Fig. 13. The FWFR's path and its body motion are presented in Fig. 14, following the diagonal line, corner to corner of the Opti-Track area. The error at the end of the trajectory in the Y -axis was found 0.1089 (m) and for the height control, the Z -axis was found 0.0121 (m). The flight time from the launching point to the final condition was found 4.5 (s).

The components of the control gain of the SDDRE using BI solution are compared with the traditional SDRE method to check the correctness of the procedure. The matrix components of $K_{1,1}(t)$ to $K_{2,4}(t)$ are illustrated in Fig. 15. The ones for $K_{2,5}(t)$ to $K_{4,6}(t)$ are presented in Fig. 16, and for $K_{5,5}(t)$ to $K_{6,6}(t)$ are shown in Fig. 17. The diagonal

Fig. 11. The position states of the FWFR flight using backward integration solution to SDDRE. (a)–(c) Position variables of the robot. (d)–(f) Euler angles.

Fig. 12. The velocity states of the FWFR flight using backward integration solution to SDDRE. (a)–(c) Translation velocities of the body. (e)–(f) Angular velocities of the FWFR.

components show higher values than the others where the match between the two methods is visible, such as $K_{1,1}(t)$, $K_{2,2}(t)$, and $K_{3,3}(t)$ which are related to the Euler angles. The motion from the terminal boundary condition to the steady state in the backward motion is also noticeable in the gain plots of the SDDRE. The components of the SDDRE matrix gain start moving backward from F, (not infinity) to the initial condition and in the steady state (close to zero) reach the result of the SDRE. This increase in gain at the final time provides more precision to track, close to the end of the trajectory. The BI motion and forward flight are shown in a series of snapshots in Fig. 18. First, the code is initiated, the robot is placed at the final condition, then moves backward to compute the BI solution. Restoring the gain and then using it in the forward SDDRE flight control. This procedure is presented in the snapshot.

The sampling time of the experimental implementation is defined as $\Delta t(i)$ which is the difference between the initial and final time of i th step. It is approximately around 0.02 (s) and an additional delay of 0.025 (s) is added to reach almost the same frequency of the actuation of the servomotors, 0.05 (s). The sampling time for reading the position

Fig. 13. The input signals of the FWFR flight using backward integration solution to SDDRE. (a) Flapping motor, (b) rudder, (c) elevator right, (d) elevator left.

Fig. 14. The flight trajectory of the FWFR flight using backward integration solution to SDDRE.

Fig. 15. The components of the SDDRE gain matrix using BI and comparison with SDRE: $K_{1,1}(t)$ to $K_{2,4}(t)$.

and orientation can be reduced; however, the possibility of the actuation is limited which defines the sampling time of the experimental control loop.

Fig. 16. The components of the SDDRE gain matrix using BI and comparison with SDRE: $K_{2,5}(t)$ to $K_{4,6}(t)$.

Fig. 17. The components of the SDDRE gain matrix using BI and comparison with SDRE: $K_{5,5}(t)$ to $K_{6,6}(t)$.

The accuracy of the state information in the backward motion (moving the bird by walking) is critical for the computation of the correct sub-optimal gain of the SDDRE for the forward loop (flight). The accuracy in position and orientation is approximately less than 2 (mm) and ≈ 0.01 (rad), respectively. The sensitivity is the alignment of the backward and forward motion. In this case study where the trajectory is a diagonal line, backward motion might be achieved easier and orientation can be maintained around the preferable flight pitch angle. If the deviation from the expected trajectory is big, the results of the gain computation will become imprecise and inadequate for forward trajectory tracking. So, in summary, the accuracy of the measurement is sufficient; however, the alignment of the backward and forward trajectories is more challenging.

Discussion. Is the practical implementation a regulation or trajectory tracking case? The performed flight in this work is a combination of regulation and tracking. The motivation of this control design is to gain more precision at the end of the flight path. So, the lateral control, Y -axis, is subjected to trajectory tracking $y_c(t) = x_c(t) \tan \psi(t_f)$. Other states are working on regulation control schemes. It was mentioned that regulation needs control for backward state regulation; however, in this practical case, there is no need for a controller. Since the robot is moved from the final states to the initial ones by a person, approximately covering the diagonal line and orientation of the robot, actuation is not needed. The last point is that if we can omit translation from the backward gain computation. The method performs control in the orientation, but the translation dynamics is coupled with Euler angles hence the orientation control has an effect on the translation one, and gain computation in backward motion must include the translation as well.

Table 4

The tracking time, error, and statistics of the flight data for 21 repetitions. “std” stands for standard deviation.

No.	t_f (s)	$ e_x $ (m)	$ e_z $ (m)	$ e $ (m)
1	5.2738	0.3874	0.2643	0.4690
2	4.1183	0.8597	0.6269	1.0640
3	4.9154	0.3712	0.2359	0.4398
4	4.7792	0.0991	0.5632	0.5719
5	5.3473	0.3877	0.5255	0.6530
6	5.4523	0.3596	0.2596	0.4435
7	4.3081	0.3799	0.3552	0.5201
8	4.5190	0.1089	0.0121	0.1095
9	3.5299	0.1317	0.3202	0.3463
10	4.2644	0.1724	0.3312	0.3734
11	4.0808	0.7264	0.0725	0.7300
12	4.3939	0.0886	0.1834	0.2037
13	4.3304	0.0307	0.2133	0.2155
14	4.1604	0.5043	0.2279	0.5534
15	4.6303	0.1100	0.0643	0.1274
16	4.3423	0.0566	0.1553	0.1653
17	4.6386	0.0658	0.1557	0.1690
18	4.6148	0.2046	0.0840	0.2211
19	4.2516	0.2084	0.1315	0.2465
20	5.0325	0.1920	0.2187	0.2910
21	4.2531	0.4163	0.1059	0.4296
Best	3.5299	0.0307	0.0121	0.1095
Worst	5.4523	0.8597	0.6269	1.0640
Median	4.3939	0.2046	0.2187	0.3734
Mean	4.5351	0.2791	0.2432	0.3973
std	0.4711	0.2224	0.1656	0.2346

6.2. Flight repeatability and statistics

The FWFR is subjected to severe disturbance by the flapping and the uncertainty in the modeling which provokes the reliability tests and suggests checking the error values for a repeated number of flights. Here in this section, the same initial and final condition with the linear trajectory is repeated for 21 attempts, presented in Fig. 19. The detailed information on the flights is reported in Table 4. The motion followed the linear diagonal path with acceptable results, shown in Fig. 19-(d). The best error in the Y -axis was found 0.0307 (m) and in the Z -axis was found 0.0121 (m). The best error in total was found 0.1095 (m). The average time of flight was determined as 4.39 (s). The standard deviation of the statistical data is reported in Table 4, presenting 0.23 for total error.

The average error of the tracking at the final point in both Z - and Y -axis was found ≈ 40 (cm). More precise regulation and tracking were also achieved in the flight trials; however, tuning in the transient zone of the flight puts severe uncertainty on the control systems. To pass the transient zone and reach steady state condition, 15 (s) flight is needed (Nekoo & Ollero, 2023a), but the average flight time in the OptiTrack area is 4.5 (s). One way to reduce the error is to increase the flight distance using a bigger area equipped with visual feedback.

6.3. Technical difficulties and challenges

The SDDRE is a nonlinear matrix-form differential equation. Since the gain and the equation are symmetric, the number of equations to be solved are $\frac{n(n+1)}{2}$ for a system with state vector of size n , or $x(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$. A simple example to show the complexity of this solution is a conventional six-degree-of-freedom (DoF) manipulator that needs 78 equations to be solved for obtaining the sub-optimal gain $\mathbf{K}(x(t))$ of the Riccati equation (Korayem & Nekoo, 2015a). Moving towards experimental implementation, these computations must be carried on a relatively short sampling time, less than the actuation frequency (approximately less than 0.1 (s) for a flapping wing robot (Nekoo & Ollero, 2023a), or 0.01 (s) for an inverted pendulum (Dang & Lewis, 2005)) to control the system. The computational burden of processors of control systems must be able to afford the sampling time, this

Fig. 18. The snapshots of the BI motion and forward flights. (a) Launching the code. (b) Moving towards the final condition. (c) Placing the robot at a final condition, with the correct approximate orientation. (d) Starting the BI. (e) Moving the robot towards the initial condition without actuation, trying to keep it on the diagonal path with the approximate desired orientation. (f) Putting the FWFR on the launcher. (g) Launching the robot with the linear guide. (h)–(k) Forward SDDRE flight. (l) Landing on the net at the end of the trajectory tracking.

Fig. 19. The repeatability tests, 21 flight attempts, and trajectory presentation. (a) The 3D trajectories of the flights. (b) The time history of motion in the Y -axis. (c) The time history of motion in the Z -axis. (d) The motion in the XY -plane.

will become an issue for lightweight onboard microcomputers such as the Raspberry Pi family. The following challenges were observed and solved during this research:

1. The first technical difficulty of this work was to code the integration algorithm of BI in a way to reach less than 0.1 (s) sampling time. The matrix/vector coding and Python program were used to achieve this task. The results reported an average value of 0.045 (s) sampling time in the majority of the experiments.
2. The integration of BI is done by receiving the updated $A(x(t))$ and $B(x(t))$ matrices with state information. This indicates if we lose

data from OptiTrack feedback, the SDC matrices will be lost and the integration will fail. This point was noticed rarely when the bird changed orientation fast by the operator on the backward motion.

The general challenges in the design, prototyping, and mechatronics of the FWFR systems were not presented since this work focused only on the control implementation of the SDDRE using BI.

The singularity topic in the SDRE/SDDRE shows itself when the SDC matrices $\{A(x(t)), B(x(t))\}$ would become singular. As long as SDC matrices, Eq. (2), present a controllable parameterization of system (1), the SDRE/SDDRE could be solved and provide a sub-optimal gain for the control law (4). Observing the SDC matrices for the FWFR in Eqs. (7) and (8), matrices $T(\xi_2(t))$, $J(\xi_2(t))$ and $C(\xi_2(t), \dot{\xi}_2(t))$ should be checked in the workspace of the robot. $J(\xi_2(t))$ is the inertia matrix, symmetric positive definite, and $C(\xi_2(t), \dot{\xi}_2(t))$ includes Coriolis and centrifugal terms, bounded and nonsingular in the workspace; however, $T(\xi_2(t))$, in Eq. (9), cannot possess zero in diagonal terms which will not allow it to be invertible $\phi \neq k\frac{\pi}{2}$ for $k = 1, 3, 5, \dots$; and also $\theta \neq k\frac{\pi}{2}$ for $k = 1, 3, 5, \dots$. The physical meaning of $\frac{\pi}{2}$ angle for the FWFR for ϕ is a roll angle of 90 degrees and for θ is vertical flight or dive; all the mentioned motions are impossible for an FWFR to achieve during a stable flight. The mentioned necessary flight assumptions (Nekoo & Ollero, 2023a), exclude the singular points from the robot's workspace. So, severe changes in orientation dynamics should be avoided to guarantee a stable flight.

7. Conclusions

This work presented a novel investigation in nonlinear closed-loop optimal control. The solution to optimal control policies has been challenging due to complex equations. One of the popular approaches for solving the optimal control is the state-dependent Riccati equation. This controller works in two modes algebraic or infinite-horizon and differential form that is the finite horizon. One classical solution to the

SDDRE, finite time control, is backward integration. The BI is implementable in finite time in the LQR; however, for the nonlinear SDDRE, it needs state information in the backward loop. Here in this work, the BI for solving SDDRE in experimental implementation was reported for the flight control of an FWFR. The computation was done onboard. The results showed the promising error of 10 (cm). Repeatability tests were performed to present statistical data for a deeper analysis of the flights. The onboard solution of the controller gains was compared with the traditional SDRE to validate the data. The results were compared with forward integration to confirm the correctness of the gain computation. The experimental flight dataset, MATLAB simulation codes, and experimental Python codes are available as supplementary material for this work.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Saeed Rafee Nekoo: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Anibal Ollero:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest for this paper

Data availability

The MATLAB codes of the simulations of this paper will be publicly available on the MATLAB Central website and as supplementary material on the journal's website. The Python codes of experimentation are also available as supplementary material on the journal's website.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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